

Atypical Presentation of Aortic Dissection in a Young Patient with Marfan Syndrome: A Case Report Highlighting Diagnostic Challenges

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ABSTRACT

Aortic dissection is a life-threatening condition that typically presents with severe chest pain, but atypical presentations can delay diagnosis and treatment. This case report describes a 24-year-old male with a marfanoid phenotype who presented with severe lumbar and abdominal pain, followed by persistent high-grade fever and hypertensive crisis. Initial evaluations ruled out infectious, gastrointestinal, and cerebrovascular causes. Transthoracic echocardiography revealed a dilated aortic root, ascending aorta, and aortic arch, with an intimal flap suggestive of dissection. Subsequent computed tomography angiography confirmed a DeBakey type I/Stanford A aortic dissection, extending from the aortic root to the iliac bifurcation, with the right renal artery arising from the false lumen. The patient underwent successful Bentall procedure for the ascending aorta and remains under surveillance for the descending aortic dissection. This case underscores the importance of considering aortic dissection in young patients with connective tissue disorders, even in the absence of classic symptoms, to prevent fatal outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Aortic dissection, Marfan syndrome, atypical presentation, DeBakey type I, Stanford A, Bentall procedure, diagnostic challenges

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INTRODUCTION

Aortic dissection is a medical emergency characterized by the separation of the aortic wall layers, often presenting with abrupt onset chest or back pain. However, atypical presentations, particularly in patients with connective tissue disorders like Marfan syndrome, can complicate timely diagnosis. 1-4

This case report details the clinical course of a 24-year-old male with a marfanoid phenotype who exhibited an unusual initial presentation of severe lumbar and abdominal pain, followed by refractory fever and visual disturbances. The absence of classic symptoms led to multiple emergency visits and delayed diagnosis. Imaging studies, including transthoracic echocardiography and computed tomography angiography, were pivotal in identifying a DeBakey type I/Stanford A aortic dissection with extensive involvement of the aortic arch and descending aorta.

The case highlights the diagnostic challenges posed by atypical presentations and emphasizes the need for a high index of suspicion in young patients with connective tissue

disorders. Early recognition and intervention are critical to improving outcomes in such high-risk populations.

Background

Aortic dissection (AD) is a critical cardiovascular emergency with high morbidity and mortality if not promptly diagnosed and treated. Classic symptoms include sudden, severe chest or back pain, but atypical presentations—particularly in patients with connective tissue disorders such as Marfan syndrome—can lead to diagnostic delays. Marfan syndrome, caused by mutations in the *FBNI* gene, predisposes individuals to aortic root dilation and dissection due to weakened connective tissue. Early recognition is essential, as missed or delayed diagnosis significantly increases the risk of fatal complications, including rupture, malperfusion syndromes, and cardiac tamponade.

Objective

This case report aims to highlight the diagnostic challenges of aortic dissection in a young patient with Marfan syndrome who presented with an unusual constellation of symptoms,

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including lumbar pain, fever, and hypertensive crisis, rather than the classic tearing chest pain. We emphasize the importance of maintaining a high clinical suspicion in high-risk populations, even in the absence of typical findings, to facilitate timely intervention and improve outcomes.

Case Report

A 24-year-old male with a marfanoid phenotype (tall stature, arachnodactyly, and pectus excavatum) presented with sudden-onset, severe (10/10) lumbar pain. Initial management included analgesics, but two days later, he developed persistent right flank and hypochondriac pain. Three days afterward, he experienced recurrent high-grade fever (40°C) with nocturnal predominance and chills, prompting multiple emergency visits where antibiotics were empirically administered without improvement. Two weeks later, he returned with uncontrolled hypertension (183/90 mmHg), transient visual disturbances, and decreased visual acuity, which resolved after blood pressure control. A non-contrast cranial CT ruled out ischemic or hemorrhagic stroke.

Due to persistent fever and worsening symptoms, he was hospitalized for further evaluation. Infectious, nephrourological, gastrointestinal, and pulmonary etiologies were excluded. Transthoracic echocardiography revealed a dilated aortic root (involving the sinuses of Valsalva, ascending aorta, and aortic arch) with an intimal flap proximal to the non-coronary cusp and distal to the left subclavian artery origin. Moderate global pericardial effusion (12 mm) was noted, raising suspicion for aortic dissection. Computed tomography angiography (CTA) confirmed a DeBakey type I/Stanford A dissection. The intimal tear measured 7 mm at the anterolateral right aortic root, with a dissection flap extending from the left common carotid artery to the iliac bifurcation. The false lumen was significantly dilated (30 mm at T5, 31 mm at T12, and 20 mm at L4), compromising the true lumen (3.7 mm at T12). The right renal artery originated from the false lumen, raising concerns for malperfusion. Additionally, a 20-mm filling defect in the false lumen suggested partial thrombosis. Figure 1

Figure 1. CTA confirmed an aortic dissection.

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The patient underwent an emergent Bentall procedure (aortic root replacement with a composite graft and mechanical valve) with successful repair of the ascending aorta. Postoperative recovery in the intensive care unit was uncomplicated, and he was discharged with plans for staged surgical intervention for the residual descending aortic dissection.

DISCUSSION

This case illustrates the diagnostic complexity of aortic dissection in Marfan syndrome, where initial symptoms may mimic other conditions, leading to delayed recognition. The patient's fever, lumbar pain, and hypertensive crisis were initially attributed to infections or musculoskeletal etiologies, underscoring the need for heightened suspicion in high-risk individuals.

Fever in AD is rare but may result from inflammatory mediators released during aortic wall injury or secondary pericardial effusion. The absence of classic tearing pain has been reported in up to 10% of cases, particularly in young patients or those with connective tissue disorders. Visual disturbances, as seen here, can occur due to transient hypoperfusion or hypertensive encephalopathy rather than direct vascular occlusion.

Imaging plays a pivotal role in diagnosis. Echocardiography is often the first-line modality, but CTA provides comprehensive anatomical details, including flap extent, branch vessel involvement, and complications like pericardial effusion. In this case, the right renal artery's origin from the false lumen posed a risk for renal ischemia, though no dysfunction was evident.

The Bentall procedure remains the gold standard for ascending aortic dissections in Marfan patients, but residual descending aortic involvement requires close surveillance or

staged repair to prevent expansion or rupture. Long-term beta-blocker therapy and serial imaging are essential to monitor aortic dimensions.

CONCLUSION

Aortic dissection should be considered in young patients with connective tissue disorders, even without classic symptoms. Unusual presentations—such as fever, isolated abdominal pain, or neurologic symptoms—demand rapid imaging to exclude this lethal condition. Early surgical intervention and multidisciplinary follow-up are crucial for optimizing outcomes in this high-risk population.

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